

Evaluating Kubernetes Batch Scheduling Systems for Containerized Declarative Data Analyses

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AUTHOR:

Xavier Tintin

SUPERVISORS:

Marco Donadoni

Tibor Šimko

ABSTRACT

REANA is as a free open-source platform designed to execute reproducible declarative data analyses on containerized compute clouds. With Kubernetes as its primary backend, it efficiently manages computational workflows through the inherent Kubernetes Job API, streamlining user job scheduling. The central goal of this openlab summer student project is directed into assessing the performance of contemporary Kubernetes batch scheduling systems like Armada, Kueue, and Volcano. We concentrated our efforts on Kueue due to its status as the Kubernetes-native scheduling solution being actively developed by the Kubernetes community. Through the use of an architecture that emulated REANA workflow submissions, we have gauged and compared scheduling solutions, focusing on performance benchmarks and supplementary capabilities like equitable resource allocation, dynamic resource adaptability, and scalability capabilities under many thousands of workloads. This evaluation aimed to assess the suitability of Kueue as a possible batch scheduler in the REANA reusable analyses platform.

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1 Introduction

Reproducibility and reusability of research data analyses are core scientific concepts that allow the sharing of knowledge and independent research validation. In the face of alarming reports that point to the inability of researchers to replicate experiments across various scientific fields, an effort of developing tools, services and strategies has been made in order to facilitate reproducible research practices [1]. This initiative extends to the field of high-energy physics, where researchers develop complex reusable physics analysis models comprising multiple computational steps to formulate and test hypotheses, thus bolstering reproducibility and knowledge preservation behind particle physics data analyses [2].

The data analysis stage in scientific research necessitates an iterative approach which is used to comprehend data sets and enhance the overall analysis outcomes. Typically, researchers rely on imperative programming, where the intricacies of the necessary calculations may often be tailored specifically to the computing platform at hand, leading to several challenges when attempting to reproduce the original analysis on different environments in the future. A suitable alternative to imperative programming is using a declarative data analysis approach, where computations are expressed as a series of codependent steps that contain a precise set of inputs and outputs. The nature of this iterative method isolates unnecessary computational details until they actually matter, therefore shedding light on "what" needs to be run rather than "how" the individual computation might be performed by the computer at hand [3].

1.1 Platform for Reproducible Analyses

One solution that addresses these challenges is the REANA platform. REANA is a reusable and reproducible research data analysis platform that enables researchers to focus on the problem domain rather than the scalable job orchestration behind running it. The use of a declarative approach to data analysis, and recent advancements in containerization technologies, provide REANA an additional advantage of being able to reuse and preserve data analyses experiments from any scientific discipline, even years after their inception [4].

The REANA platform consists of two main components: a client used by the researchers and a cluster that executes the computations on the target platform based on client requests. This dual-component architecture allows the user to directly interact with the system and instantiate, launch, and monitor computational workflows, run on supported compute backends such as Kubernetes [5]. The workflow environments are fully encapsulated by the means of using software containers and seamlessly dispatched to cloud compute backends based on their high-throughput or high-performance computing needs.

Currently, REANA relies on the native Kubernetes Job API to schedule and manage user workloads on Kubernetes clusters. When a user initiates a workflow, either through the REANA client or REST API, the system is notified of the user's request to start a specific workflow. This request is processed by the REANA platform, which leverages Kubernetes for workflow execution and management [4]. In an effort to explore potential alternatives to REANA's scheduling system, this report delves into the evaluation of contemporary Kubernetes batch scheduling systems within the REANA ecosystem, with Kueue as selected candidate. Utilizing a setup that mirrors REANA's workflow submissions, we conducted a comprehensive assessment of the Kueue workflow scheduler, highlighting performance benchmarks, resource allocation, dynamic adaptability, and scalability under substantial workloads.

1.2 Kueue

In the realm of managing computational workloads in a Kubernetes cluster, Kueue emerges into prominence as a Kubernetes-native system wielding the power to manage quotas and how jobs consume resources within a cluster [6]. This scheduling system decides the behaviour of the Kubernetes jobs that are submitted to a cluster, addressing their creation, deletion, and preemption. This level of fine-grained control over job scheduling and resource management introduces Kueue as an enticing alternative to REANA's scheduling system.

Kueue introduces a set of versatile APIs that empower users to define quotas and policies for fair resource sharing among tenants. Its resource fungibility feature allocates Kubernetes jobs utilizing alternative resource configurations when the preferred ones are fully utilized. These concepts collectively shape Kueue's resource management and workload orchestration framework.

2 Implementation

To ensure a meaningful comparison between the REANA scheduler and Kueue, it became imperative to architect a Kueue deployment setup that emulates a workflow submission akin to that of the REANA platform [7]. This approach will create a meaningful and direct comparison between both scheduling systems.

2.1 Emulating Workflow Submission

To effectively replicate the workflow submission process observed in the REANA platform, our design approach entailed the submission of a Kubernetes Job, that in turn, spawns another Kubernetes Job within the same designated namespace. In essence, this emulation comprises two Kubernetes Jobs:

1. **Workflow Submission Job:** This job functions as the "workflow engine" within REANA, responsible for orchestrating all the steps and jobs within a workflow. It serves as the central control point for managing the entire workflow.
2. **Workflow Task Job:** The second Kubernetes Job symbolizes an individual step within the workflow. It represents the execution of a specific task or job as part of the larger workflow orchestrated by the Workflow Submission Job.

Furthermore, as depicted in Figure 1 the design is encompassed within a Kubernetes namespace named "reana" that houses two LocalQueues. Each LocalQueue is responsible of grouping related workloads, one dedicated to the representation of workflow submissions and the other dedicated to task submissions. These LocalQueues, in turn, are associated with ClusterQueues, which point to specific Resource Flavors. Given the utilization of homogeneous resources, we establish a default resource flavor to support the emulation effectively.

In addition to this emulation framework, it's essential to highlight two crucial configuration aspects that play a crucial role in assessing the scheduling systems' behavior. First, we implement a queuing strategy of StrictFIFO, ensuring that workloads are processed in a strict first-in, first-out order based on their priorities and creation timestamps. This choice not only aligns with the REANA platform's default behavior but also provides a structured foundation for evaluating scheduling efficiency. Furthermore, it's essential to mention that both ClusterQueues in our setup are configured with a cohort, demonstrating Kueue's inherent support

Figure 1: A visual representation of the Kueue architecture used in this study, illustrating the key components such as LocalQueues, ClusterQueues, Resource Flavors, and the Cohort configuration. Note the separate workflow submission queue and the workflow task queue which were created to simulate typical REANA workflow execution scenario.

for resource sharing, a feature that could prove beneficial for REANA in the future. However, it's noteworthy that, as part of our current configuration, we have consciously set the borrowing limit to 0 for both ClusterQueues. This deliberate choice explicitly prohibits any borrowing of unused quota among ClusterQueues at this time, ensuring that resource sharing is disabled when both ClusterQueues are fully utilizing their allocated resources. This decision added an extra layer of rigor to this evaluation, ensuring a clear assessment of the core capabilities and limitations of both scheduling systems.

2.2 Workflow Execution in Kueue

In the implementation of the Kueue scheduler, the workflow execution follows a well-defined sequence of interactions between Kueue and the Kubernetes cluster. This orchestration begins when a user initiates a workflow run via `kubect1`. Kueue initiates the process by promptly creating the initial workflow submission job in a "suspended" state, while continuously monitoring resource availability within the Kubernetes cluster. Once adequate resources become available, the Kubernetes cluster takes control and generates the first workflow pod, which then records its starting timestamp.

This initial workflow pod communicates with Kueue to request the creation of the workflow task job, and the process iterates, with Kueue handling the creation and suspension of the second job until resources allow its execution. Upon starting, the second sleep job pod logs timestamps of its start and end before termination. The first workflow pod, upon recognizing the termination of the second sleep job terminates itself. This intricate sequence of events emulates the workflow execution process in REANA where workflow engines spawn new workflow jobs as necessary for the proper execution of the workflows until all their tasks are completed.

Workflow execution in Kueue's design demonstrates the platform's ability to intelligently manage the scheduling and execution of multiple jobs and workflows within a Kubernetes cluster. The "StrictFIFO" queuing strategy combined with Kueue's resource monitoring and pod suspension mechanisms ensures optimal resource allocation and workflow execution. Kueue not

representative workload when evaluating system performance and scalability. Whilst apparently simple, its duration is unusually short for a real physics payload, hence it stresses the workflow scheduling system much more than a regular physics payload would, hence its suitability for testing scheduling performance.

- **Node Expansion:** To comprehensively assess Kueue’s scalability, we have planned a progressive cluster node expansion by doubling the number of nodes after each experiment, scaling from 2 to 4, 8, 16, and 32 nodes.
- **Workflow Scaling:** In parallel with node expansion, the number of workflows for each experiment was tripled. This scaling allowed us to explore the system’s performance under varying workloads, simulating CPU-bound workloads (when running 128 concurrent workflows) and memory-bound workflows (when running 384 concurrent workflows) on cluster nodes with 8 cores and about a 12 GiB RAM per node.
- **Performance Metrics:** This evaluation includes measuring the total walltime from workflow initiation to completion. This approach allowed us to assess whether the progression follows a linear pattern as the number of available nodes were being increased during experiments.
- **Memory Allocation Considerations:** To carefully manage memory allocation and node capacity, the number of workflows and memory settings was adjusted to match the capabilities and constraints of our compute backend.

These practical evaluation guidelines strike a good balance between realistic simulations and efficient Kueue performance testing when scheduling either CPU-bound or memory-bound user workloads.

4 Results

Figure 3 shows the result of one computing experiment described in the previous section where we were scheduling 384 workflows in a cluster composed of 32 nodes. The graph highlights two distinct phases represented in orange and blue. The orange segment represents the time a workflow spends in a pending state before it can be executed by the cluster. The blue segment indicates the time a workflow spends in the running state, executing the task to sleep for 30 seconds. This phase doesn’t significantly benefit from parallelization, as the workload inherently involves a fixed task duration. Adding more resources or nodes to the cluster can lead to running more of these workflows concurrently. Note that when the cluster gets busy, the “sleep for 30 seconds” task can actually take close to two minutes to execute.

Figure 4 shows the result of similar experiment when we tried to schedule 2000 workflows, simulating over-charge. It is noteworthy that all the workflows finished successfully, yet the cluster encountered notable resource allocation constraints that led to virtually halting execution of user workloads for several minutes, as evidenced by the lengthened "blue regions".

We have performed many experiments such as depicted in Figures 3 and 4 using clusters with varying number of nodes. It is to be expected that larger clusters can run the same workloads faster than smaller clusters. We have been specifically varying node counts (2, 4, 8, 16, 32) for both 128 and 384 concurrent workflows and measuring the total experiment execution wall time. This allowed to gain insight into the scheduling speed-ups as the clusters get larger.

Figure 3: The visual representation of experiment’s execution progress when 384 workflows were asked to start using a Kubernetes cluster of 32 nodes. Note the workflow scheduling delays from the moment of workflow submission until they can be executed (displayed in orange). The workflow runtime is then displayed in blue. The later workflows take longer to execute than the former ones due to the cluster resources being busy; yet the execution progresses steadily.

Figure 4: The visual representation of experiment’s execution progress when 2000 workflows were asked to start using the same Kubernetes cluster as in Figure 3. Note the time period from about 15:50 until about 15:55 when the execution of the hworkflows was not progressing due to cluster resource congestion.

Figures 5 and 6 visually depict these speedup trends for 128 and 384 workflows, respectively. It is noteworthy that we didn’t observe a significant increase in speedup beyond the introduction of 16 nodes for both 128 and 384 workflow scenarios. This phenomenon can be attributed

Figure 5: Speedup of experiment execution time when running 128 test workflows on clusters with progressively increasing number of nodes.

Figure 6: Speedup of experiment execution time when running 384 test workflows on clusters with progressively increasing number of nodes.

to several factors. Firstly, as the number of nodes increases, the concept of "diminishing returns" in parallel computing comes into play. Beyond a certain point, the marginal difference between using 16 nodes and 32 nodes suggests that other factors, such as resource constraints or overhead, may start to impact the speedup gains more prominently than the benefits of additional nodes. Secondly, the specific nature of the computational workload also plays a crucial role. If the tasks within the workflows exhibit limited parallelizability or the dependencies that cannot be easily parallelized, the system's ability to harness additional nodes effectively diminishes. These combined factors explain the observed limited speed-up benefits beyond 16 nodes, highlighting the importance of optimizing workload parallelization and resource allocation in parallel computing scenarios.

5 Discussion

Kueue, as a Kubernetes Native scheduler system, stands out as a promising candidate for supplementing or even replacing the REANA scheduler, offering the advantage of seamless integration with Kubernetes infrastructure. This native compatibility instills confidence in its ability to efficiently manage computational workloads in a Kubernetes-based environment. Throughout our evaluation of Kueue, we have identified several areas that highlight its potential for long-term adoption.

5.1 Challenges and Scalability Considerations

One issue that surfaced during our evaluation is related to Kueue's use of random characters appended to the end of pod names when creating a pod from a job specification. This occasionally led to naming collisions among pod names when many jobs were submitted to the system. This behavior can be addressed and is somewhat expected given the limited differentiation within pod names. We have reported these findings to the upstream open-source community, fostering collaboration for ongoing improvements and refinements [9].

Furthermore, our exploration of Kueue revealed an intriguing limitation. In certain scenarios involving extensive job queues, Kueue faced challenges when handling workloads surpassing

approximately 10,000 jobs, even with no naming collisions. These observations indicate that memory exhaustion plays a role in this constraint. Thus, it is essential to investigate whether Kueue requires more resources than currently allocated, such as a dedicated node with additional memory.

5.2 Job Suspension Delays in High Workload Scenarios

In the course of these experiments, a critical observation emerged when the number of submitted pods and workflows increased significantly. While the master node of the cluster appeared capable of maintaining stability, the node with the `kueue-system` pod faced memory-related issues, leading to segmentation violation and out-of-memory (OOM) situations and resulted in the abrupt termination of processes due to memory exhaustion. A particular concern was the recurrent crashes and panics in the Kueue manager’s logs, primarily attributed to memory errors. This resulted in a “CrashLoopBackOff” where the Kueue manager pod could not be easily restarted. It is noteworthy though that this only occurred when the Kueue cluster was expressly over-stressed to the full. Our experiments helped to shed light on the intricate balance between workload volume, memory resources, and system stability within a Kubernetes cluster subjected under high concurrent workload. As a potential future improvement, relocating Kueue to a dedicated node with larger memory flavour could be explored as a strategy to address these high-stress-situation challenges.

5.3 Future Work

There are areas of potential exploration in Kueue’s capabilities and the challenges uncovered throughout this study. Expanding on Kueue’s support for diverse resource configurations could enhance its adaptability, accommodating a wider spectrum of computational workloads and hardware profiles. This expansion would enable Kueue to offer more precise job allocation and optimization, catering to a wider array of use cases and resource constraints.

Additionally, replicating the study using realistic particle physics analysis examples would be desirable. Such examples usually tend to have longer-running workflow jobs which may prove to be easier to schedule than the current model, retaining the Kueue advantages whilst limiting its drawbacks.

6 Conclusions

In this evaluation of the Kueue batch scheduling system within a Kubernetes cluster, we uncovered valuable insights on its performance and scalability. Kueue exhibits promising capabilities for efficient job scheduling and resource management, aligning well with the needs of the REANA platform. While our experiments illuminated areas of potential drawbacks, such as Kueue memory management, they also highlighted Kueue’s potential for integration into REANA’s ecosystem. With further corner case testing and experimentation to fine-tune deployment setups, Kueue could become a valuable addition to REANA’s repertoire, offering features and flexibility that may prove advantageous in future scenarios. Notably, Kueue’s ability to leverage different resource flavors, including specialized GPU nodes, opens the door to expanded capabilities that REANA can take advantage of when executing containerized declarative data analyses.

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